

PROBE WG2

“Recommendations for measurement-product requirements for data assimilation and long-term reanalysis of multi-variable ABL profiling dataset.” - Deliverable 2.3

D2.3: Organize critical review of minimum measurement-product requirements for assimilation and long-term reanalysis relevant to the different stakeholder groups. Implement tools for NWP data

assimilation and long-term reanalysis. Coordinate the exploitation of the developed tools for data assimilation experiments and long-term multi-variable reanalysis for climatology and climate monitoring purposes.

Project start date	10/2020
Project end date	04/2024

Project title (acronym)	Deliverable 2.3
Authors	Document preparation conducted by P. Martinet and J-F. Ribaud Authors (by alphabetical order): C. Augros, P. Chambon, A. Haefele, Z. Mariani, P. Martinet, C. Merker, A. Schomburg, D. Turner

1 INTRODUCTION

During the PROBE Cost action, international collaboration made possible an extensive use of new dataset from field experiments and new tools developed towards the assimilation of ground-based remote sensing. New tools have also been developed in order to get an easier access to dataset from different instruments at several instrumented sites in Europe. In this report, the section 2 provides recommendations for the assimilation of observations sensitive to thermodynamic properties. This section aims at reviewing the minimum requirements for data assimilation and long-term reanalysis of temperature and humidity products. This review should help to identify necessary developments needed to foster data assimilation of temperature and humidity products from ground-based remote sensing and UAVs or identify solutions to coordinate a more extensive use of already existing products.

In section 3, the development of new tools to access different datasets over Europe with standardized and harmonized data processing are presented. These tools

should ensure a high level of quality control to create a multi-parameter dataset easily usable by the scientific community. These developments are necessary to enhance the use of ground-based surface networks over Europe for several key applications: evaluation of numerical weather prediction, climate change monitoring, process studies, satellite CAL/VAL activities.

2 MAIN REQUIREMENTS FOR TEMPERATURE AND HUMIDITY PRODUCTS FOR DATA ASSIMILATION PURPOSE

2.1 INTRODUCTION

This document aims at reviewing the minimum requirements for data assimilation and long-term reanalysis of temperature and humidity products. This document should help to identify necessary developments needed to foster data assimilation of temperature and humidity products from ground-based remote sensing and UAVs or identify solutions to coordinate a more extensive use of already existing products.

As already reviewed in deliverable 2.1, several ground-based instruments provide complementary information on temperature and humidity in the atmospheric boundary layer (ABL):

- Active sensors provide vertical profiles with a better vertical resolution but cannot provide information within and above clouds due to the attenuation of the lidar signal. They also suffer from a “blind zone” which is in general between the surface and 50 m or as high as a few hundreds of meters. In this document we focus mainly on water vapor lidars (Raman LIDAR (RAM) or DIAL technology)
- Passive instruments do not suffer from any blind zone which makes them sensitive to the very lowest layers of the atmosphere but have a coarser vertical resolution compared to active instruments. Hyperspectral infrared spectrometers (IRS) provide more information on the vertical structure compared to microwave radiometers but their signal is totally attenuated within optically thick clouds similarly to lidars. Microwave radiometers (MWR) have the possibility to provide vertical profiles in all-sky conditions well resolved for temperature in the boundary layer but with a poor description of the vertical structure for water vapor.

In addition to ground-based remote-sensing instruments, UAVs now offer new possibilities for automatic and high temporal frequency sounding in the ABL.

Depending on the chosen approach either level2 products (retrieved temperature and humidity from ground-based instrument) or level1 raw data (brightness temperatures for passive instruments, lidar backscattered power or temperature and humidity

measurements for UAVs) can be directly assimilated into numerical weather prediction (NWP) models.

2.2 LIST OF EXISTING DATA ASSIMILATION OR LONG-TERM REANALYSIS STUDIES CLASSIFIED BY INSTRUMENT

This section aims at providing a synthesis of already existing data assimilation or long-term reanalysis experiments where level1 or level2 data from MWR, IRS, UAVs or water vapor lidars have been assimilated.

Abbreviations:

EnKF: Ensemble Kalman Filter

LETKF: Local Ensemble Transform Kalman Filter

3D-Var: Three-Dimensional Variational Assimilation

QPF: Quantitative Precipitation Forecast

FSS: Fraction Skill Score

DWL: Doppler Wind Lidar

OSSE: Observing System Simulation Experiments

DA: Data Assimilation

References	Instrument	Product	Quick synthesis
Otkin 2011 Hartung 2011 <i>DOI: 10.1175/2011MWR3622.1</i> <i>DOI: 10.1175/2011MWR3623.1</i>	DWL MWR AERI RAM	Temperature Profiles Humidity Profiles Wind profiles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - OSSE (simulated data) - 140 profile stations in the USA - ENKF - DA for 1 day in winter - Largest impact on analysis and short-term forecasts when wind included with T/Q
Caumont 2016 <i>DOI:10.1002/qj.2860</i>	MWR	Temperature Profile Humidity Profile	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Real data - 13 MWR stations - AROME 3D-VAR every hour - 41 days - Small impact except for QPF for larger rainfall accumulations.
He 2020 <i>DOI: 10.1080/16742834.2019.1709299</i>	MWR	Temperature and Humidity Profile	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Real data - 2 stations - 4 days assimilation - WRF DA every 6 hours - Improved distribution and localisation of precipitation
Thomas et al 2024 (in review, QJRMS)	MWR	Temperature profile	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Real data - 6 stations - AROME 3DVAR every hour

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3 months experience in winter - Improvement in the temperature bias up to 6 hour forecasts - Improvement of fog scores based on surface visibility
<p>Leuenberger 2020, <i>DOI: 10.1175/BAMS-D-19-0119.1</i></p>	<p>Raman Lidar UAVS</p>	<p>Temperature and humidity profiles</p>	<p><u>Raman Lidar:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - LETKF - 1 day experiment - Convective system associated with a cold front - Improved forecasts of precipitation up to 24 hours <p><u>UAVs:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Winter fog (6 cases) - LETKF - 3 UAVs profiles up to 1800m - Simulation of a much larger fog area with UAVs assimilated at 00 UTC compared to satellite images. - Neutral impact when strong synoptic-scale forcing
<p>Qi et al 2022 <i>DOI: 10.3390/atmos13010074</i></p>	<p>MWR</p>	<p>Temperature Profile Humidity Profile</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - RMAP-ST assimilation system - WRF 3DVAR - 5 real stations - 1 day experiment: heavy precipitation case - Improved representation of precipitation and heat urban island before rain.
<p>J. Vural C. Merker A. Schomburg <i>DOI: 10.1002/qj.4634</i></p>	<p>MWR</p>	<p>Brightness temperatures</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2 Direct assimilation 3 LETKF 4 Two different setups: MeteoSwiss presents the operational assimilation of two stations, Deutscher Wetterdienst presents experiments focusing on selection of channels and vertical localisation with one station only 5 Positive impact on model analyses: the impact on the brightness temperature is positive, so the match of brightness temperature between model and observations is improved after assimilation.

			<p>6 Neutral impact on forecasts: the impact on model prognostic variables is more difficult to achieve, results are still not fully satisfying, more work is needed on the assimilation side.</p>
<p>Hu et al 2019, DOI: 10.1175/WAF-D-18-0200.1</p>	<p>AERI DWL</p>	<p>-Temperature and humidity profiles from AERI</p> <p>-Horizontal Wind from the Doppler Wind Lidar</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Single case study of tornado in USA great plains. - WRF model at 3km resolution. - Inflation technique of the ENKF. - Six sites with AERI and DWL - Depending on the inflation technique used in the DA system, the convective initiation can be forecast with the assimilation of AERI and DWL observations - More impact from the assimilation of the AERI moisture field compared to wind observations - Largest impact when both AERI and DWL assimilated together
<p>Degelia et al 2020 DOI: 10.1175/MWR-D-20-0118.1</p>	<p>AERI DWL</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Temperature and humidity profiles from AERI - - Horizontal Wind from DWL 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Six stations over the US Great Plains - 13 case studies of nocturnal convective initiation (CI). - GSI-based EnKF system. - Small but consistent improvement with all verification metrics with the assimilation of thermodynamic profilers. - Degradation often observed when assimilating wind observations probably due to the under-estimation of wind profiler observation errors.
<p>Lewis et al, 2020: DOI:10.3390/atmos11070729</p>	<p>AERI</p>	<p>Temperature and humidity profiles</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - One case study of severe convective weather event - WRF EnKF - One station - Improved FSS scores in the first hours of forecast with the assimilation of AERI data.
<p>C. Augros / P. Brousseau (Météo-France) on going</p>	<p>Raman lidars</p>	<p>Humidity Profiles (Specific Humidity)</p>	<p>monitoring and assimilation experiments for 5 water vapor lidars (French and Spanish Mediterranean coasts) => assimilated</p>

			variable = specific humidity - AROME 3D-EnVar - Autumn 2022
--	--	--	---

Table 1. Synthesis of published papers where level1 or level2 data from MWR, IRS, UAVs or water vapor lidars have been assimilated.

Additional references:

Coniglio et al 2019, DOI: 10.1175/MWR-D-18-0351.1

Degelia et al 2019, DOI: 10.1175/MWR-D-18-0423.1

2.3 MAIN REQUIREMENTS IN TERMS OF DATA FORMAT/PRECISION AND TEMPORAL RESOLUTION

In this section, the main requirements in terms of data format / precision and temporal frequency are listed from the WMO OSCAR requirements. Only requirements for high resolution and nowcastings models are listed as this is where we can expect the largest impact from ground-based remote sensing network.

Additional requirements were included based on the actual needs expressed by data assimilation experts: one for temperature and two for brightness temperature (for direct assimilation purposes).

NWS refers to National Weather Services.

Variable	Data format	Precision	Observing cycle	Vertical Resolution	Timeliness
Temperature High Resolution NWP	BUFR	G: 0.5 K	G: 15 min.	G: 100 m	G: 10 min.
		B: 1 K	B: 60 min.	B: 250 m	B: 30 min.
Temperature Profile Intermediate Needs for NWS	BUFR	0.8 K	30 min.	< 500m	20'
Temperature Nowcasting	BUFR	G: 0.5 K	G: 5 min.	G: 100m	G: 5 min.
		B: 1 K	B: 10 min.	B: 300m	B: 10 min.
Specific Humidity High resolution NWP	BUFR	G: 2%	G: 15 min	G: 100 m	G: 15 min
		B: 5%	B: 60 min	B: 200 m	B: 30 min

Specific Humidity Nowcasting	BUFR	G: 2%	G: 5 min	G: 100 m	G: 5 min
		B: 5%	B: 10 min	B: 300 m	B: 10 min
Brightness temperatures Humidity Channels	BUFR	1 K	30 min.	/	20 min.
Brightness Temperatures Temperature Channels	BUFR	0.5 K	30 min.	/	20 min.

Table 2. Lines colored in light pink show the list of WMO OSCAR requirements for the atmospheric boundary layer and high-resolution/nowcasting NWP application areas. Only two requirement levels are reported here for each parameter: goal (G) and breakthrough (B). From: <https://space.oscar.wmo.int/variables>. An intermediate need for temperature has been included based on PROBE members expertise in data assimilation as well as requirements needed for brightness temperatures.

For data assimilation in NWS it appears that the most important requirements are the precision, the observation cycle and timeliness. The precision should be better than the actual NWP background errors in order to positively impact the analyses and forecasts.

The observation cycle and timeliness should be short enough in order to receive the observations in time to be assimilated in each assimilation cycle (at least one per hour).

2.4 SPECIFIC REQUIREMENTS AND TOOLS RELATED TO DATA ASSIMILATION SYSTEMS

Current operational data assimilation systems rely on several assumptions that must be satisfied in order to correctly assimilate new observations to obtain a positive impact on weather forecasts. When raw level1 measurements are directly assimilated instead of derived products, fast observation operators are also needed to translate model variables into the observation space. This section aims at summarizing the main requirements and/or tools that are already available or need to be developed to foster data assimilation of ground-based remote sensing observations related to temperature and humidity.

- **Channel or vertical level selection:** Variational data assimilation system or Ensemble Kalman Filters make use of an observation error covariance matrix which is often considered as diagonal. In such cases, observation errors (either brightness temperatures (BT) for level1 data or derived temperature and humidity profiles for level2 data) must be uncorrelated. For passive instruments (MWR / IRS), some correlations might exist between BT

measured at the same channel but at different elevation angles. The same appears in derived temperature and humidity profiles where the vertical grid of the product is often higher than the true resolution of the retrieval. To facilitate data assimilation, it is important to provide information about observation error correlations to help national weather services in the selection of the passive channels or vertical levels that can be truly considered as un-correlated.

Several methods already exist to provide this information, among them we can cite:

- **DFS method** (based on the Degrees of Freedom of the Signal): with this method, only vertical levels that are a full DFS apart are selected for data assimilation (Turner and Löhnert 2021, DOI: 10.5194/amt-14-3033-2021). This method is only possible when vertical profiles are derived with optimal estimation approaches (that can also be called one dimensional variational methods).
- **Inter-level error covariance method**: in this method the true vertical resolution is directly inferred from differences between the retrieved profiles and considered truth profiles from reference measurements like radio-sounding observations (Liljegren et al 2005, DOI: 10.1109/TGRS.2004.839593) => several databases of co-located MWR and RS profiles exist to calculate this covariance but there is no public dissemination of the results to end-users.

It is important to note that main NWP centers have recently been working at the integration of non-diagonal observation error covariance matrices in their systems. This is for example the case at ECMWF for some microwave radiometers and for hyperspectral infrared sounders. In that case, it is important to provide assimilation teams with an estimation of observation error covariances. If a full matrix can be used within the assimilation system, this step of observation thinning (either in brightness temperature space or retrieved profile space) can be avoided.

- **Specification of observation errors**: For all data assimilation systems, observation errors covering instrumental error, forward operator and representation error must be specified. Degelia et al 2020 demonstrated clearly that an erroneous specification of observation errors can lead to a degradation of the forecast skills when assimilating new observations in current NWP models. A good specification of observation errors is thus essential to pave the way for an improvement of NWP forecasts through the assimilation of new observations. For the specification of instrumental errors, brightness temperature and radiance errors can be provided by manufacturers (derived after calibration). For MWR, the RPG manufacturer now includes the delivery of the observation error covariance matrix within the manufacturer software. For IRS radiance observations, the spectral random error is also a direct output of the calibration routine (Revercomb et al. Applied Optics 1988).

When retrieved profiles are assimilated, the expected uncertainty is provided by optimal estimation approaches for each profile to users. In the case of multi-variate regressions or neural networks, an estimation of the expected errors can be provided through the use of the test database (sample of profiles not used during the training of the coefficients but used to evaluate the expected accuracy of the retrieved profiles). However, these errors are often under-estimated compared to the true uncertainty. In fact, they generally use simulated measurements within the training. Simulated measurements are then perturbed according to the expected instrumental errors. However, each instrument has its own instrumental errors and the profile uncertainty also depends on the instrumental weighting functions, whose position depends on the atmospheric conditions. One challenge for the assimilation of future ground-based networks will be that observation errors are in general instrument dependent (even for the same type of instrument).

For forward operator errors, Cimini et al 2018 (DOI: 10.5194/acp-18-15231-2018) propose an approach to estimate the absorption model uncertainty due to uncertainty in the spectroscopic parameters. The approach has been applied to microwave frequencies (20-60 GHz) and provides now references for forward model uncertainties. For IRS radiance observations, a fast forward model still needs to be developed for a direct assimilation of radiance observations.

Representativeness errors have also to be specified and are still an unresolved issue. In fact, the footprint of the remote sensor is usually much smaller than the horizontal resolution of the model. Thus, the observation could see a cloud that is smaller than the horizontal spacing of the model. Thus, if we assimilate the BT or radiances, then the model must be able to build subgrid scale clouds. Due to the difference between the observation footprint and model resolution, poorer performance can also be observed near coastlines or complex terrain compared to the assimilation over flat and land-locked terrain.

As assimilation algorithms do not need to separate the sources of errors (instrumental errors, forward model errors, representativeness errors), diagnostics like the Desroziers (Desroziers et al 2005, DOI: /10.1256/qj.05.108) algorithm can be useful to tune these errors (this diagnostics can be used after a first assimilation experiment run with a first approximation of observation errors and estimates the total full observation error covariance matrix).

- **Bias correction**: the bias correction of observations is an important step before data assimilation whatever the assimilation system as data assimilation algorithms assume un-biased observations. NWS prefer to use their own bias correction scheme (sometimes adaptive) as the bias correction also depends

on the chosen observation operator. However, providing information on a first estimation of the instrument biases appears to be relevant for the assimilation teams. The observation minus background monitoring developed by Météo-France and using the fast radiative transfer model RTTOV-gb appears to be well suited for an implementation at the European scale (through E-Profile and ACTRIS infrastructure). This tool based on De Angelis et al 2017 (DOI: 10.5194/amt-10-3947-2017) has already been used for several instruments at different locations in France and Europe (Cologne, Lindenberg, SOFOG3D and PANAME experiments). This methodology needs to be tested for IRS.

The methodology needs to be tested for the assimilation of retrieved profiles too.

- **Forward operators:** When assimilating brightness temperatures (BT) or radiances, forward operators are needed to convert the model variables into equivalent BT. The adjoint of the tangent linear is also necessary for a fast computation of Jacobians (derivatives of the BT with respect to model control variables). For MWR measurements, the fast RTTOV-gb model was developed (De Angelis 2016, DOI: 10.5194/gmd-9-2721-2016). Additional validation is probably necessary for low elevation angles as RTTOV-gb was derived from the satellite version of RTTOV which is not optimized for low elevation angles. For IRS radiance observations, a fast forward model still needs to be developed for a direct assimilation of radiance observations.
- **Time averaging:** observations from remote sensors are generally available at a high temporal resolution (like 1 sec.). Information about the most relevant time averaging could help the users when assimilating the data.
- **Localization:** For the LETKF, the brightness temperature data needs to be assigned to a specific height. The observation can also be assimilated without localizing the information in height allowing the observation to impact the whole model profile. This tends to lead to a slight change in temperature and humidity profiles smeared out over the whole height. When a sharper localisation is used, a localized substantial impact in one height region can be observed with potentially beneficial impact. Additionally, a localisation range needs to be specified to indicate in which height range around the location of the measurement it should be considered for the analysis. For the height assignment and the localisation range, the most important information is the height region from which the information in the brightness temperature comes from. More detailed information could be very helpful here for data assimilation team to increase the benefit of new observations. One approach is to use the Jacobians provided by fast forward models like RTTOV-gb for example.
- **Background-error-covariance-matrix:** For current data assimilation systems, the accuracy of the analysis and the benefit of remote sensing

observations depends on the specification of the background-error-covariance matrix **B**. This matrix specifies how much weight is given to the a priori profile compared to the observation, specifies how the information from the localized observation is spread in the model space both vertically and horizontally (for 3D/4D-Var assimilation), and imposes the balance between the model control variables. It is now well known that background covariances highly depend on the atmospheric conditions. In fact, fog or convective conditions will exhibit different behaviors compared to clear-sky conditions in terms of vertical correlations and variable cross-correlations (Martinet et al 2020, DOI: 10.5194/amt-13-6593-2020, Marquet et al 2022, DOI:10.5194/amt-15-2021-2022). A good prescription of vertical correlations dependent on the atmospheric boundary layer height is also crucial to avoid the spread of punctual observations over a large region where atmospheric variables are no longer coupled. For variational data assimilation, the use of ensemble data assimilation to derive a spatially and weather-dependent **B** matrix that mimics in a variational context the approach taken in the stochastic ensemble Kalman filter should help a more appropriate assimilation of ground-based remote sensing instruments. As demonstrated in Hu et al 2019 (DOI: 10.1175/WAF-D-18-0200.1), the impact of the assimilation of IRS and DWL observations assimilated through an EnKF algorithm depends on the inflation technique used to take into account the ensemble under-dispersion. For variational assimilation schemes, similar issues can appear due to the under-dispersion of ensemble members used to derive the flow-dependent **B** matrix especially within the atmospheric boundary layer. A good representation of the **B** matrix is a key challenge for observations sensitive to the boundary layer transition and evolution.

3 ROADMAP ON REANALYSIS OF LONG-TERM, MULTIVARIATE TIME SERIES BASED ON REOBS AND OTHER METHODS FOR FUTURE IMPLEMENTATION ON NETWORKS

3.1 KEY MESSAGE

Today, many applications such as climate variability studies, process understanding, numerical model evaluation (global or regional) and satellite mission assessments require to access data sets comprising long-term series of high-quality, standardized, harmonized, and spatially and temporally homogeneous measurements.

- Several European and worldwide observation networks, facilitated by data centres, collect high-quality data on atmospheric physico-chemical processes from the surface to the upper troposphere, spanning through the boundary layer.

- Despite their potential, these databases remain under-exploited. Conducting multi-year, multi-variable, and multi-site studies to understand variabilities and their representativeness poses challenges for users due to several reasons:
 - The completeness of datasets as initially described may be compromised, with missing files, periods, or variables.
 - File formats might vary over time (e.g., NetCDF, ASCII).
 - Inconsistent (pre-)processing of variables/products over time.
 - Inadequate control of data quality within files (e.g., outliers from level 0 data).
 - Heterogeneous nomenclatures and metadata over time.
- Tools/products like ReOBS or ARMBE can homogenize and standardize these data, ensuring a high level of quality control to create a multi-parameter dataset easily usable by the scientific community. These tools feed directly into the various data centres of the observation networks mentioned above.
- Given the complexity of processed data, these tools are typically multifunctional. They enable assessment of databases managed by data centres but cannot replace them entirely. Instead, they assist in ensuring complete, consistent, and high-quality data over time.
- The initial datasets harmonized through ARMBE and ReOBS show promising potential for end-users, resolving previously identified issues. Scaling these valuable datasets across extensive network sites requires significant efforts in automating and adapting configurations and quality controls. However, these tools are hindered by limited methods to address missing data, automatically detect anomalies, or correct biases. In this context, with abundant data from various observation networks, artificial intelligence (AI) presents new avenues for reconstructing long-term, homogeneous, and high-quality datasets.

3.2 INTRODUCTION

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) simulations exhibit a considerable divergence among models in forecasting future global climate, as well as in replicating the observed current climate. These uncertainties are more pronounced at regional scales and shorter timescales (e.g., seasonal scale), which are crucial for impact assessment. Notably, models struggle to accurately depict inter-annual and seasonal variability and extremes in temperature and precipitation. Incorporating atmospheric observations is essential for enhancing our understanding of the processes underlying temporal variability and simulation uncertainties. These observations should encompass a wide array of atmospheric variables across different spatial and temporal scales.

Multi-annual and multi-variable datasets from ground-based observations are invaluable resources, offering comprehensive and precise information spanning several decades. Despite their scientific significance, data from observation networks are underutilized, particularly in harnessing observed synergy due to complexities in calibration procedures, quality control, data treatment, and temporal representativeness.

Integrating atmospheric observations from ground-based observatories can enhance our understanding of climate processes and improve the accuracy of climate simulations. However, leveraging these observations effectively requires addressing technical challenges and comprehending the complex interactions between local-scale processes and broader climatic phenomena.

In addition, it is imperative for satellite measurements to have access to datasets of high quality controlled that are both spatially and temporally consistent. These datasets play a vital role in calibrating and validating satellite measurements accurately. Unfortunately, these data sets are either lacking or too limited in number. Note that at the opposite the space research community already worked on homogenized and reanalysed products that have recently been released (e.g.

<https://climate.esa.int/en/about-us-new/climate-change-initiative/>,

https://www.cmsaf.eu/EN/Highlights/Dokumente/News_15.html).

3.3 AVAILABLE TOOLS AND REQUIREMENTS

An important homogenization work is thus needed for these observations (section 2a). There are two main type of methods available today for the research community to robustly process ground-based data at an hourly timescale over more than a decade (sections 2 b-c).

a) Requirements

There are requirements to be followed by the different instrumented sites that would like to obtain a multi-parameter dataset with a high level of quality control (data and metadata).

About the data (if not already in data centres [i.e. level 0]):

- 7 The data must be directly measured geophysical quantities or derived from algorithms. In the latter case, it is necessary to provide the references of the algorithms used.
- 8 If they exist, it is necessary to provide additional information such as quality flags on the context of the measurement (the instrument, the observation, breakdown period, drift...), other control parameters or any information having an influence on the data or the measurement. It is also important to mention if the instrument has been subject to a technological upgrade over the years.
- 9 Input files can be in text format (ASCII, CSV...) or NetCDF.
- 10 The filename should be different for all files.
- 11 It is important to have no temporal overlap within and between the different files.
- 12 Timestamp should be in UTC.
- 13 No time drift is recoverable (the acquisition system must be synchronized to a time server).
- 14 Source files can be daily, monthly or yearly.
- 15 The altitude of the measurements must be temporally homogeneous and in meters Above Ground Level.
- 16 The database must remain accessible in order to guarantee the reconstitution of the data set at any time.

About global metadata :

Write station name and/or its respective ID

Name of the institution where the file was created (ACTRIS, BSRN, GRUAN, ...).

GPS coordinates of the measuring station latitude and longitude in DMS (degrees, minutes, seconds).

Altitude of the station, and altitude of the instruments in relation to the ground in meters.

Membership (if any) of the measurement in a national or international network.

Examples of both global and variable attributes are given in Figures 1-2.

```
[attrs]
title = SIRTA ReOBS meteoairsol_air dataset
summary = The 20-year-long SIRTA-ReOBS dataset is contained in a single netCDF file
containing mean values of more than 150 physical variables. Variables entering the ReOBS
dataset are quality controlled at their native time resolution. The objective of ReObs
is also to respect the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)
in particular the Reusable aspect which is more obvious for a production chain.
keywords = GCMD: ATMOSPHERE,GCMD: AEROSOLS,GCMD: AIR QUALITY,GCMD: ATMOSPHERIC
PRESSURE,GCMD: LAND SURFACE/AGRICULTURE INDICATORS,GCMD: ATMOSPHERIC RADIATION,GCMD:
ATMOSPHERIC TEMPERATURE,GCMD: ATMOSPHERIC WATER VAPOR,GCMD: ATMOSPHERIC WINDS,GCMD:
CLOUDS,GCMD: PRECIPITATION,GCMD: DATA ANALYSIS AND VISUALIZATION,GCMD:
CALIBRATION/VALIDATION,GCMD: DATA ANALYSIS,GCMD: STATISTICAL APPLICATIONS
keywords_vocabulary = GCMD
Conventions = CF-1.7, ACDD-1.3, ISO 8601
naming_authority = AERIS data center
source = AERIS data center,ACTRIS-FR,SIRTA,Meteo-France
comment = Technical and scientific staff of SIRTA site discuss with AERIS data center
staff to develop the quality check and provide the metadata information concerning
variables and instruments.
acknowledgement = The ReOBS database is maintained by the French national center for
Atmospheric data and services AERIS. We extend our acknowledgments to the technical and
computer staff of SIRTA Observatory for taking the observations and making the data set
easily accessible.We also thanks the ACTRIS-FR Research Infrastructure for their support
in this study.
license = Inspired by CC-BY
standard_name_vocabulary = CF Standard Name Table v76
creator_name = AERIS data center
creator_type = Data center
creator_url = https://www.aeris-data.fr/
institution = AERIS data center
project = AERIS data center,ReOBS
program = ACTRIS-FR
references = https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-10-919
2018,https://doi.org/10.1002/2014GL060205,https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-012-1469-
y,https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-00329353
publisher_name = AERIS data center
publisher_type = Institution
publisher_url = https://www.aeris-data.fr/
processing_level = See ATBD
metadata_link = https://reobs.aeris-data.fr/
```

Figure 1 : Example of typical global attributes associated with the final file.

```
[ta]
long_name = Air temperature
standard_name = air_temperature
units = Celsius
instrument = guilcor_pt100(20140101-now)
comment = sensor installed at 2m agl inside no ventilated shelter
coverage_content_type = physicalMeasurement
```

Figure 2 : Exemple of typical variables attributes associated with the final file.

Note that these data homogenization and standardization tools are at the end of the data lifecycle chain. In fact, these tools are designed to feed directly into the various existing data centres (ACTRIS, BSRN, GRUAN, AERONET, etc.), providing direct, easy access to all data from Levels 0 to 2 (L0-L2). Databases remain sometimes heterogeneous due to software and instrumental changes, presenting significant potential if homogenized and standardized. This means that all files must use the same version of the processes applied, and that there must be no legacy files. Tools such as ReOBS and ARMBE (see section 2b, 2c) can provide valuable feedback to data centres on one of these issues, but should never be used as a substitute.

b) ReOBS

The prefix "Re" of ReOBS denotes six principal steps for ground-based observations: calibration, quality control, algorithmic processing, hourly averaging, standardization of data formats and metadata, and expert scientific analysis.

The ReOBS project (<https://reobs.aeris-data.fr/en/welcome/>) aims to produce a multi-parameter dataset with rigorous quality control measures, formatted for easy utilization by the scientific community in studying and comprehending regional climate variables. It seeks to aggregate, analyse, and standardize all observations, such as those from an ACTRIS National Facility or other, into a single NetCDF file with hourly time resolution (Figure 1). The ReOBS file is designed to adhere closely to CF and GCMD conventions for metadata, as well as the FAIR principles.

The ReOBS tool:

- Adapts to the raw input data provided by ground-based observations sites.
- Implements advanced quality control procedures to identify and eliminate erroneous data, as documented in an ATBD available upon request.
- Conducts temporal and/or spatial averaging of the data.

- Generates a comprehensive, merged, and well-documented NetCDF file.

Figure 1 : ReOBS a new approach to synthesize long-term multi-variable dataset.

c) ARM-BE

In the same vein as ReOBS, and having begun few years earlier, the equivalent product developed in the USA is called ARMBE for Atmospheric Radiation Measurements Best Estimate.

The ARMBE data product, formerly known as the Climate Modeling Best Estimate (CMBE), consolidates essential cloud, radiation, atmospheric, and surface/land property data from ARM instruments into a single dataset (Acquerman et al 2003; Xie et al., 2010). Aimed at fostering increased utilization of ARM data in climate research and model development (<https://www.arm.gov/>), ARMBE offers a comprehensive collection of well-observed quantities commonly utilized in model evaluation. For more than twenty years, ARM ground-based instruments such as cloud radars, micropulse lidars (MPLs), laser ceilometers, microwave radiometers (MWRs), and solar and infrared radiation stations (SIRSSs) have measured these quantities. Specifically designed for climate modelers, ARMBE features hourly temporal resolution akin to typical climate model output, including standard deviations within averaged hours and quality control flags to indicate data variability and quality.

ARMBE's detailed observations of clouds and their broader atmospheric context across various climate regimes contribute significantly to process studies aimed at enhancing cloud parameterization in climate models. Moreover, its long-term dataset with high temporal and vertical resolutions facilitates the examination of climate

variability, change, and the statistical evaluation of climate models. ARMBE also serves as input for several ARM value-added products (VAPs), such as ARM Diagnostics for Climate Model Evaluation (ADCME) and large-scale forcing data from constrained variational analysis (VARANAL).

Comprising two components, ARMBEATM and ARMBECLDRAD, ARMBE provides essential atmospheric data and detailed cloud and radiation quantities, respectively. However, it's important to note that ARMBE represents single-point measurements, necessitating statistical methods for comparison with climate model outputs, which often represent grid-box means over 100 kilometres. Despite stringent quality control measures, ARMBE still encounters data quality issues inherent in the VAPs used to generate it, including Active Remote Sensing of Clouds (ARSCL), Data Quality Assessment for ARM Radiation Data (QCRAD), and Microwave Radiometer Retrievals (MWRRET).

3.4 EXISTING DATASETS ACROSS THE EUROPEAN ECOSYSTEM

The two methods presented above are flexible enough to adapt to different datasets. In view of the issues raised in the introduction to this document, a number of observation networks could easily benefit from the added value of these tools. Here we make a review of some of Europe's or world's high-potential networks.

a) ACTRIS

The Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure (ACTRIS) is a pan-European research infrastructure (RI) that generates high-quality data and information concerning short-lived atmospheric constituents and the processes influencing their variability in both natural and controlled environments (<https://www.actris.eu/>).

The atmosphere operates through intricate chemical and physical mechanisms, and accurate predictions rely on sophisticated models grounded in observational data. ACTRIS plays a crucial role in refining emission source uncertainties, understanding deposition processes, and quantifying their ecological impacts. It also contributes vital insights into global biogeochemical interactions and climate-ecosystem feedback loops. Additionally, ACTRIS aids in identifying sources of air pollutants affecting

human health and complements Earth Observations from space, providing essential ground-truthing for satellite data.

ACTRIS offers access to high-quality atmospheric data and advanced facilities. It develops technologies for climate and air quality modelling, benefiting diverse users in research, space agencies, and more. ACTRIS fosters community integration to achieve common goals and meet user needs efficiently.

Currently, ACTRIS consists of 22 countries, 112 national facilities, and 6 topical centers, which the latter serve as essential operational entities within this research infrastructure. These centers play a crucial role by offering services to users in line with ACTRIS access policies, providing operational support to National Facilities to enhance their performance, and contributing to ACTRIS governance and management.

Figure 2 : World and Europe maps of the various ACTRIS National Facilities, respectively.

b) BSRN

The Baseline Surface Radiation Network (BSRN) serves as the central archive for radiation measurements, accompanied by surface and upper-air meteorological observations and station metadata. BSRN (<https://bsrn.awi.de/>), a project of the Global Energy and Water Exchange (GEWEX), aims to detect changes in Earth's

radiation field related to climate change. Its data are vital for validating satellite and computer model estimates. With stations in various climatic zones, BSRN measures solar and atmospheric radiation with high accuracy and time resolution (Figure 3). In 2022, BSRN renewed its commitment to Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) activities and was recognized as a GCOS network for global surface radiation measurements.

c) GRUAN

The Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) Reference Upper-Air Network (GRUAN) is an international network of sites dedicated to measuring essential climate variables above the Earth's surface (<https://www.gruan.org/>). It addresses a crucial gap in the global observing system by providing long-term, high-quality climate data from the surface to the stratosphere. These measurements are utilized to analyse trends, validate data from other observing systems like satellites and radiosonde networks, and investigate atmospheric processes. GRUAN aims to

expand to 30-40 sites globally, leveraging existing observational networks and capabilities where feasible (Figure 4).

d) AERONET

The AERONET (AErosol RObotic NETwork) program, established by NASA and LOA-PHOTONS (CNRS), along with various networks and collaborators, has provided a comprehensive database of aerosol properties for over 25 years. This database supports aerosol research, satellite retrieval validation, and synergizes with other databases. AERONET (<https://aeronet.gsfc.nasa.gov/> and Figure 5) ensures instrument standardization, calibration, and data processing. It offers globally distributed observations of spectral aerosol optical depth (AOD), inversion products, and precipitable water in different aerosol conditions, categorized into three data quality levels: Level 1.0 (unscreened), Level 1.5 (cloud-screened and quality-controlled), and Level 2.0 (quality-assured).

3.5 RESULTS AND POTENTIAL APPLICATIONS

The ARMBE product has already been used in 54 publications since the creation of its first dataset, which continues to grow year after year. For instance, Zheng et al. 2023 demonstrated the usefulness of having a long-term, homogeneous and standardized dataset of very high quality to assess the performance of climate models in reproducing simulated clouds and surface short-wave radiation.

Ground-based observations from six Atmospheric Radiation Measurement (ARM) user facility sites are used to statistically assess the performance of cloud and radiation simulations in climate models from the Coupled Model Inter-comparison Project Phase 5 (CMIP5) and their successors in Phase 6 (CMIP6), originating from 10 different modelling institutes. The study reveals model biases in simulating clouds and radiation and identifies improvements and degradation in model performance from CMIP5 to CMIP6. Insights into parametrization issues and physical processes aid in future climate model development (Figure 6).

Similarly, Cheruy et al. (2013) emphasizes the importance of evaluating land-atmosphere interactions in climate models to mitigate uncertainty, presenting a new method to assess boundary layer, convection, and cloud parametrizations within the Earth System Model (ESM) developed by the Institut Pierre Simon Laplace (IPSL). The study examines two different land surface hydrology parametrizations and compares ten-year simulations of the coupled land surface/atmospheric ESM modules with observations from a ReOBS-SIRTA (Site Instrumental de Recherche par Télédétection Atmosphérique (Haeffelin et al. 2005) - which is an ACTRIS National Facility) near Paris (<https://sirta.ipsl.fr/>). By refining the model grid and adjusting the large-scale circulation, the study identifies areas where parametrizations perform poorly and affect regional climate simulations. It highlights factors contributing to

biases in near-surface variables and demonstrates how new parametrizations can improve model performance.

Another example, small-scale processes such as surface–atmosphere interactions and cloud feedbacks are considered crucial for understanding near-surface temperature variations (Chiriaco et al., 2014). ReOBS-SIRTA facilitates this understanding by providing a multi-variable synergistic compilation, allowing for the study and comparison of various atmospheric or surface characteristics (Bastin et al., 2018). Building on this foundation, Rojas et al. (2021) further explore the specific impact of clouds on local 1-hour surface temperature variations in the Paris region, utilizing the comprehensive dataset provided by ReOBS-SIRTA.

Finally, a first intercomparison of the evolution of aerosol optical thickness in Europe was carried out on 3 ACTRIS sites (Granada [Spain], Lindenberg [Germany], and SIRTA [France]) thanks to the synergy of 3 different ReOBS (Figure 7). Assuming that optical thickness is directly linked to air quality and PM10 concentration (as a proxy), we can see that the same trends are found at the various European sites. A general decrease in aerosol optical thickness is thus observed, confirming the overall improvement in air quality across Europe in recent decades.

3.6 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

As discussed in this document, standardized, homogeneous, and high-quality datasets are crucial for linking with climate and regional models or for evaluating space missions.

ARMBE (ARM Best Estimate) and ReOBS are projects/tools that provide standardized datasets with hourly temporal resolution, incorporating quality control measures, and adhering to metadata conventions, catering to the needs of the scientific community for evaluating global and regional climate models and enhancing climate research efforts. These initiatives meet the expectations for standardized, accessible data to advance climate studies and model development. Note that in a context where carbon footprint monitoring associated with new measurement (and campaigns) is gaining in importance, these tools enable both measurements and results from recent decades to be reinterpreted, making them easier to use and promoting instrumental synergy.

The ReOBS approach outlined in this paper is being extended to other super-sites. Presently, efforts are being made to apply this approach to data from national facilities within the ACTRIS infrastructure, particularly the Lindenberg site in Germany (with over 100 years of measurements) and the Granada site in southern Spain. Additionally, discussions are ongoing regarding the application of ReOBS to other ACTRIS national facilities. Other ongoing initiatives include integrating the ReOBS dataset into the OBS4MIP (Observations for Model Intercomparisons Project) database, dedicated to comparing observational data with CMIP simulations.

Also, new collaborative effort between the USA and Europe, known as CARGO-ACT, is set to commence in spring 2024. This collaboration aims to bring together the ARMBE and ReOBS tools, showcasing the strength of these high-quality datasets for the research community through joint synergies at various sites worldwide (ARM and ACTRIS). This collaboration is expected to materialize in the coming months.

Despite the immense value of these datasets produced by ARMBE or ReOBS tools, effectively scaling them across vast networks of sites demands substantial efforts in automating and customizing configurations and quality controls. Ensuring consistency and accuracy across diverse sources and environments is a challenge.

Existing tools face limitations in addressing critical issues such as missing data, anomalies detection, and bias correction, which can impede the reliability and usefulness of the datasets. Missing data necessitates robust imputation techniques to fill gaps without introducing biases. Anomaly detection demands sophisticated algorithms to distinguish irregularities from noise, helping in flagging significant events or errors. Bias correction requires tailored methodologies to maintain dataset integrity by adjusting for systematic errors, ensuring the accuracy of analyses and predictions. With abundant data from those observation networks, artificial intelligence (AI) presents new avenues for enhancing data quality and utility. Leveraging AI can help revolutionize data quality assurance, enabling more accurate analyses on various atmospheric fields.